

BUSINESS PROCESSES OF MARKETING LOGISTICS IN WHOLESALE TRADE

Kholmamatov Diyor Haqberdievich

Assistant professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service, Samarkand, Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *The role of marketing logistics as a modern marketing technology in the system of goods movement, business processes of marketing logistics, implementation of value creation for enterprises and customers in marketing logistics business processes is focused on. Wholesale trade is emphasized as the main business line of marketing logistics.*

Keywords: *marketing, logistics, marketing logistics, sales, supply, business processes, value chain, supply chains, goods movement, stock of goods.*

БИЗНЕС-ПРОЦЕССЫ МАРКЕТИНГОВОЙ ЛОГИСТИКИ В ОПТОВОЙ ТОРГОВЛЕ

Аннотация. *Акцентируется внимание на роли маркетинговой логистики как современной маркетинговой технологии в системе товародвижения, бизнес-процессах маркетинговой логистики, реализации создания ценности для предприятий и клиентов в бизнес-процессах маркетинговой логистики. Особое внимание уделяется оптовой торговле как основному направлению маркетинговой логистики.*

Ключевые слова: *маркетинг, логистика, маркетинговая логистика, продажи, снабжение, бизнес-процессы, цепочка создания стоимости, цепочки поставок, товародвижение, товарный запас.*

The development strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 in the direction of rapid development of the national economy and ensuring high growth rates includes the development of industrial cooperation between large industries and regional enterprises, the production volume of locally competitive products goals such as increasing, finding new strategic markets, proportional development of regions are set [1]. The implementation of these goals makes the issue of organizing and managing the movement of goods and material resources in the country's economy even more urgent.

Along with the formation of modern concepts of marketing, in the mid-1990s, the term "marketing logistics" began to be used theoretically in scientific sources. F. Kotler (1998), a leading specialist in marketing, emphasizes that the strategic problems of distribution of goods, which are an important component and element of marketing, are related to logistics and marketing. [8]. F. Kotler emphasized that the term marketing logistics is being used more and more in recent times, and it includes not only the process of movement of goods from the producer to the consumer, but also the delivery of goods and materials from suppliers to enterprises. showed in his studies [8].

Russian scientist G.L. Bagiyev (1998) included the term marketing logistics in his explanatory dictionary of marketing. G.L. Bagev interpreted marketing logistics as a method that ensures the harmony of logistics and marketing activities in the optimization of all types of flows [2].

Polish specialist Dwiliński (1998) describes marketing logistics as a system of goods movement that guarantees the timely delivery of ordered goods in accordance with logistics and marketing, using the appropriate means of transport, in the shortest time and at the lowest cost [7].

After 2000 years, research and views on marketing logistics gradually increased. Scientific views on business processes of marketing logistics were also formed. For example, M. Christopher and H. Pecklar (2005) focused on business processes of marketing logistics in their research.

In business processes, the introduction of the concept of marketing logistics in modern practice is gaining momentum. In their research, M. Christopher and H. Pecklar justified the need to pay attention to integration processes in solving functional obstacles in order for enterprises to be market-oriented [9]. The content of marketing and logistics in business processes is widely and sufficiently studied in modern literature. But the issues of marketing logistics in business processes have not been sufficiently studied.

M. Christopher and H. Peck were the first to propose a classification of marketing logistics business processes [9]. According to their classification, the business processes of marketing logistics are as follows:

- brand development (including new product development);
- development of relations with consumers (mainly, creation of loyalty of end consumers);
- customer management (creating interactions with intermediaries);
- improving relations with suppliers (strengthening mutual relations in the supply chain);
- supply chain management (including order fulfillment).

Experts Ryszard Barcik and Marcin Jakubiec (2013) define marketing logistics as a system of marketing mix (product policy, price policy, sales policy, movement policy) and logistics mix (transportation, warehousing, stock organization, packaging, order fulfillment and service). has shown in his research that it serves to satisfy the needs of customers at a high level [10].

Russian specialists A.A. Trifilova and A.N. Voronkov (2011) defined marketing logistics as starting from the initial source of material flows (raw materials, spare parts, materials), planning production, physical distribution of finished products, delivering finished products to effectively meet the needs of consumers and describes operational management activities [11].

The role of marketing logistics in the organization of trade is given special attention in the scientific researches of A.N. Germanchuk. It was A.N. Germanchuk who showed the aspects that clearly connect marketing and logistics in trade marketing, sales activities, and developed a model of business processes for ensuring the competitive advantage of marketing logistics [4].

The wholesale trade turnover in the country's economy also has a growing trend. In the 9th month of 2022, the wholesale trade turnover is 152277.8 billion. soums, the growth rate was 118.4 percent. Also, the share of non-food products in the wholesale turnover is increasing.

Further development of wholesale trade turnover, establishment of inter-sectoral trade cooperation are urgent issues. Today, wholesale trade enterprises and organizations face serious competition. Because manufacturers and retailers are actively implementing direct purchase programs as a result of the use of digital technologies. In order for wholesale trade enterprises and organizations to achieve success, they must adapt their high-level services in time to the changing needs of customers (manufacturers, retailers).

For this, wholesale trade enterprises and organizations should have a modern storage system, information technology, improve the level of service, means of delivery and a strong marketing service. This requires the harmonization of marketing and logistics functions based on a modern approach in wholesale trade enterprises and organizations.

Improving the efficiency of business processes in wholesale trade is directly related to marketing logistics. Today, logistics includes management of trade operations, analysis of supplier and consumer markets, coordination of demand and supply in the market of goods and services. It can be seen that marketing issues and logistics issues are connected.

Marketing logistics is based on combining the ideas of marketing and logistics. Marketing logistics in wholesale trade is aimed at forming a portfolio of orders, planning the production range based on it, determining the optimal technology of movement of products, creating standards for product quality and packaging, eliminating time losses during delivery, and effective use of material and labor resources.

Modern information technologies play an important role in wholesale trade marketing logistics. Digital technologies, wholesale terminals, uniform coding of goods, tracking the movement of goods via satellite, computerization of warehouse operations, electronic data exchange and money transfers are implemented in wholesale trade through marketing logistics.

The task of marketing logistics in wholesale trade is to manage the supply of the manufacturer, the flow of finished products from the manufacturer to the consumer. Marketing logistics in wholesale trade is the analysis, planning, organization and management of all operations related to product storage, delivery, movement route, communication, order portfolio formation, service provision.

In wholesale trade, marketing logistics is very important to improve the efficiency of goods movement and reduce costs. Marketing logistics is the design and implementation of infrastructure in wholesale trade, which involves the efficient and cost-effective delivery of goods from the point of origin to the point of sale.

Marketing logistics provides the marketing service of production enterprises, logistics companies and other inter-sectoral cooperation of the economy in carrying out operations such as purchase of goods in wholesale trade, storage, delivery, after-sales service, creation of reserves.

To develop marketing logistics in wholesale trade, it is advisable to implement the following:

1. In order to develop marketing logistics in wholesale trade, it is necessary to establish integrated business cooperation in the "production-consumer" chain. Organization of intermediate warehouses between producers and intermediate enterprises. It is necessary to improve the mechanisms for the organization of stockpiles, packaging, packing, and delivery on the basis of cooperation and outsourcing.

2. When developing a business process model of marketing logistics, it is necessary to pay attention to designing an optimal system of goods movement in market-oriented supply and distribution chains. The main part of the goods moving in the supply chains passes through wholesale trade. The design of business processes related to the movement of goods in supply chains on the basis of marketing logistics also affects the development of wholesale trade.

3. The development of marketing logistics ensures the satisfaction of consumer needs through high-quality service, forming a value creation system for the consumer by coordinating the functions of the participants of the distribution channels. Ultimately, by optimizing the costs of the goods movement system, the profitability of marketing activities is increased.

4. When designing a business process model of marketing logistics, functional elements, namely marketing functional elements (market research, assortment policy, price strategies,

promotion, sales promotion) and logistics functional elements (order management, transportation, warehouse, stock management) to organize a system based on compliance.

5. To theoretically and scientifically substantiate that as a result of the application of marketing logistics in wholesale trade, competition shifts from goods to buyers, from functions to processes, from operations to relations, from resources to knowledge, from profit to efficiency, from enterprise to distribution channels.

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 of January 28, 2022 "On the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" // www.lex.uz
2. Bagiev G.L. Marketing: dictionary and bibliography. SPb: Izd-vo SPbGUEF, 1998. – 74 p.
3. BLAIK, P., 2001: Logistyka. Koncepcja zintegrowanego zarządzania, wyd. II, PWE, Warszawa.
4. Germanchuk, A. N. Spetsifika organizatsii trade-marketinga na predpriyatii / A. N. Germanchuk // Fundamentals and examples of research in the modern world: mater. XXVII Mejdunar. nauch.-prakt. conference, Oct. 15, 2019 - SPb. : Strategiya budushchego, 2019. – S. 58-61.
5. Golikov E.A. Marketing and logistics - new instruments of economy. - M. : Izdatelstvo "Examen", 2006. - 220 p.
6. CIESIELSKI, M., 1999: Logistyka w strategiach firm, PWN, Poznań.
7. DWILIŃSKI, L., 1998: Wstęp do logistyki, Oficyna Wydawnicza PW, Warszawa.
8. Kotler, P. (1998) Marketing Management: Analysis, Planning, Implementation, and Control. 9th Edition, Prentice Hall, Upper Saddle River.
9. Christopher, M. Marketingovaya logistics / M. Christopher, H. Peck. ; per. English I. Kasimova. - M. : Izdatelsky Dom "Technology", 2005. - 200 p.
10. Ryszard Barcik, Marcin Jakubiec (2013). Marketing logistics. <https://docplayer.net/4272544-Marketing-logistics-bielsko-biala-poland-email-rbarcik-ath-bielsko-pl-bielsko-biala-poland-email-m-jakubiec-ath-bielsko-pl.html>
11. Trifilova A.A., Voronkov A.N. Marketing logistics. Uchebnoe posobie. Nizhegorod. Mr. archit.-stroit. un-t – N. Novgorod: NNGASU, 2011. – 83 p.
12. Ergashxo'jayeva Sh.J. Innovation marketing. Darslik.-T.: Cho'lpon nomidagi NMIU, 2014. – 176 b.
13. Musayeva Sh.A., Usmanova D.I. Problems of Marketing in the System of Higher Education. Academic Journal of Digital Economics and Stability, 2022
14. Musayeva Sh.A., Usmanova D.I., Usmanov F.Sh. Innovative Strategies Of Tourism Development In Uzbekistan. European Journal of Innovation in Nonformal Education (EJINE), 2022
15. Musayeva Sh.A., Usmanova D.I., Usmanov F.Sh. Problems with Marketing Research in the Furniture Market. Eurasian Journal of Academic Research, 2021
16. Musayeva Sh.A., Usmanov F.Sh. Ways to expand network marketing and e-commerce in the wholesale of medicines. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793